

Photosynthesis of Nitrogenous Compounds.

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In a series of papers Baudisch (*Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 1009; 1913, **46**, 115; 1917, **50**, 652) first investigated *in vitro* the photo-formation of nitrogenous compounds by exposing a mixture of formaldehyde and potassium nitrate or nitrite to radiations from a mercury vapour lamp. Instead of formaldehyde, he sometimes used methyl alcohol. He reported the formation of formhydroxamic acid and its potassium salts in his experiments, and an alkaloidal substance was also obtained but he could not identify it as the amount was exceedingly small. He seemed to have also obtained pyrrol and pyridine derivatives in very small quantities.

Baly, Heilbron and Stern (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **123**, 165), after exposing ammonia solutions, saturated with carbon dioxide to radiations from a quartz-mercury vapour lamp, seemed to have obtained methylamine and pyridine. According to Baly and co-workers, if ammoniacal solutions of cupric carbonate saturated with carbon dioxide are used, methylamine and pyridine or piperidine are formed. When 2M solutions of formaldehyde and ammonia are exposed to ultraviolet light from 6 to 10 days, a solid brown substance giving the reactions of the alkaloid coniine is reported to be formed along with other products already mentioned. Snow and Stone (*ibid.*, 1923, **123**, 1509), however, have stated that the evidence of Baly, Heilbron and Stern (*loc cit.*) for the formation of pyridine and coniine is inconclusive.

Dhar and Sanyal (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, **29**, 926), by exposing ammonia, carbonic acid and formaldehyde for 20 hours to sunlight, could obtain methylamine but no pyridine. On exposing ammonia, formaldehyde and cupric carbonate for 80 hours to tropical sunlight, they obtained methylamine and an alkaloidal substance the identity of which could not be established as the amount was small.

It will be evident, therefore, that some complex nitrogenous substances have been obtained by the action of light on a mixture of formaldehyde and nitrite or ammonia in presence of catalysts. But the amounts being exceedingly small, the results are not very definite

and not exactly reproducible. Moreover, the view has been advanced that the synthesis of proteins can take place in the dark provided carbohydrate is available and that the nitrogen assimilation is not a photochemical process.

In view of this unsatisfactory position of the problem of the photosynthesis of nitrogenous compounds, a systematic work on this line has been undertaken in this laboratory. In this communication, we are recording our results obtained on the photosynthesis of methylamine and nicotine, on exposing formaldehyde and ammonia with different catalysts to tropical sunlight.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2% Solutions of Merck's formaldehyde after distillation were mixed with small amounts of concentrated ammonia and were exposed to sunlight for a long time in presence of different catalysts, *e.g.*, zinc oxide, titanium oxide, copper carbonate, nickel carbonate, etc. After the necessary exposure, the solutions were filtered and distilled over a sand-bath. The amine was tested for in the distillate. The residue left in the flask was treated with ether. The ether extract was shaken with dilute sulphuric acid. If any basic substance were present, it would come in the aqueous layer, which was made alkaline and again shaken with ether. In our experiments, the second ethereal extract was very small and it smelt like tobacco. Hence, we suspected the presence of nicotine but as a large amount of hexamethylenetetramine is also formed by the action of ammonia and formaldehyde and as this substance showed all the tests of alkaloids, precautions were taken to remove hexamethylenetetramine from the mixture. We have observed that the precipitate obtained by the addition of mercuric chloride solution to hexamethylenetetramine is white but the precipitate with nicotine is yellow, which dissolves readily in dilute acetic acid, but the white precipitate obtained from hexamethylenetetramine and mercuric chloride is not readily soluble in dilute acetic acid. This is how we could separate a small quantity of nicotine from hexamethylenetetramine.

In order to find out whether any nitrogenous compound is formed in the absence of light, blank experiments with the reacting substances and catalysts in the same proportions were carried on in vessels kept in the dark for the same period as in light. The reacting substances kept in the dark were also analysed according to the

method already mentioned, but in no case could we detect the presence of methylamine or any nitrogenous compound except hexamethylenetetramine.

TABLE I.

Experiment.	Time of exposure to sunlight.	Results.
1. 2% Formaldehyde (150 c.c.) and 6.2 <i>N</i> -ammonia (6 c. c.) and cupric carbonate (6 g.) in three sealed bulbs	80 hr.	Hexamethylenetetramine, methylamine and nicotine obtained
2. 2% Formaldehyde (500 c.c.) and 6.2 <i>N</i> -ammonia (15 c.c.) and cupric carbonate (5 g.) in two pyrex glass beakers	120	Hexamethylenetetramine, methylamine and an oily substance of nicotine smell obtained
3. 2% Formaldehyde (500 c.c.) and 6.2 <i>N</i> -ammonia (10 c.c.) and cupric carbonate (5 g.) in a glass trough	110	Hexamethylenetetramine, methylamine and nicotine obtained
4. 2% Formaldehyde (200 c.c.) and 6.2 <i>N</i> -ammonia (4 c.c.) and titanium oxide (4 g.) in three sealed bulbs	80	Do
5. 2% Formaldehyde (2000 c.c.) and 6.2 <i>N</i> -ammonia (25 c.c.) and titanium oxide (5 g.) in a big enameled dish	120	Do
6. 2% Formaldehyde (2000 c.c.) and 6.2 <i>N</i> -ammonia (25 c.c.) and titanium oxide (5 g.) in a big enameled dish	130	Do
7. 2% Formaldehyde (500 c.c.) and 6.2 <i>N</i> -ammonia (10 c.c.) and zinc oxide (5 g.) in a glass trough	90	Do
8. 2% Formaldehyde (2000 c.c.) and 6.2 <i>N</i> -ammonia (25 c.c.) and zinc oxide (5 g.) in a big enameled dish	130	Do

The nicotine was obtained as the hydrochloride and all the standard tests were applied. In order to be definite that the substance obtained is practically pure nicotine hydrochloride, we determined the molecular weight by igniting known weights of the dry chloroplatinate of the base and the following values of the molecular weights were obtained.

TABLE. II.

Chloroplatinate.	Platinum obtained.	M. W. found.	Actual M. W. of nicotine.
1. 0.0041 g.	0.0011 g.	158.68	162.13
2. 0.0569	0.0152	160.25	
3. 0.0612	0.0163	161.35	

It appears, therefore, that we have been able to obtain nicotine practically in a pure condition by exposing formaldehyde and ammonia with catalysts like cupric carbonate, titanium oxide, zinc oxide etc., for a long time to sunlight. But cupric carbonate seems to be the best catalyst.

In most preparations, after filtering the solution and distilling the filtrate, methylamine was obtained. Methylamine could be detected by the carbylamine test and by the melting point of the hydrochloride.

We are of the opinion that in the photosynthesis of nitrogenous compounds, in order to get positive evidence, the following points should be noted :

(a) The temperature of the reacting mixture may not exceed 35°. (b) Better yield of the nitrogenous compound is obtained if the incident radiation is rich in ultraviolet radiations. (c) The intensity of the light must be high.

We carried on some experiments with a mercury vapour lamp and after an exposure lasting for 25 hours, a mixture of 2% formaldehyde (500 c. c.) and 10 c. c. of 6.2N-ammonia without any photocatalysts yielded methylamine and nicotine.

DISCUSSION.

From the researches carried on in these laboratories, we are of the opinion that formaldehyde is actually formed from carbon dioxide and water vapour by the absorption of light. In a recent communication Dhar and Atma Ram (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 287) have reported that from 0.001 to 0.00015 g. of formaldehyde is present per litre of freshly collected rain-water and they have attributed the presence of formaldehyde in rain-water to its photo-formation from carbon dioxide and water vapour present in the atmosphere. Moreover, the above authors (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1932, **206**, 171) have obtained larger yields of formaldehyde by the photo-reduction of

carbonic acid and bicarbonates by metals like cerium, magnesium, etc. Also there is the possibility of the generation of formaldehyde by the photo-decomposition of carbohydrates, organic acids and other organic substances. It is well known that ammonia and its compounds occur in the atmosphere and these are washed down to the soil by rain-water. In recent communications (Rao and Dhar, *Soil Science*, 1931, 31, 379; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, 199, 422) it has been shown that ammonia and its compounds present in the atmosphere and in the soil are converted into nitrite by their oxidation by air in presence of sunlight. Hence, in nature, formaldehyde and nitrite or ammonium salts react forming the basis of complex nitrogenous substances. Also the sugars present in the plants may undergo partial oxidation to mucic acid. It has already been stated that some investigators have reported the formation of pyridine on exposing a mixture of formaldehyde and nitrite or ammonia solutions. It seems likely that pyridine derivatives of the nature of β -aminopyridine may also be formed by the condensation of methylamine and formaldehyde. The mucic acid and the β -aminopyridine may form nicotine passing through different stages.

It is interesting to note that Pictet, and Rotschy (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 1225) have already synthesised *laevo*-nicotine corresponding to the natural alkaloid starting from β -aminopyridine and mucic acid in the laboratory in the absence of light.

Attempts are being made to find out whether the photosynthesised nicotine is optically active or not. The photosynthesis of other nitrogenous compounds is in progress.

As no nicotine or methylamine could be obtained by keeping the reacting substances in the same proportions in the dark under conditions similar to those kept in the light, we believe that light is essential for the formation of methylamine and nicotine from formaldehyde and ammonia. It appears, therefore, that the view that the synthesis of complex nitrogenous compounds is not photochemical in nature, is incorrect.

SUMMARY.

1. By exposing 2% solutions of formaldehyde and small quantities of ammonia in presence of catalysts, *e.g.*, copper carbonate, zinc oxide, titanium oxide, etc., to sunlight or to radiations from a mercury vapour lamp, methylamine and nicotine have been obtained.

2. Nicotine can be separated from hexamethylenetetramine, which is always obtained in large quantity in these reactions by the solvent action of dilute acetic acid on the yellow derivative obtained with solutions of mercuric chloride and nicotine. This derivative of nicotine dissolves readily in dilute acetic acid solutions, whilst the hexamethylenetetramine compound obtained with mercuric chloride is white and is insoluble in dilute acetic acid.

3. The molecular weight of the photosynthesised nicotine was determined by igniting known weights of the chloroplatinate of the base and weighing the platinum. The mean value of the molecular weight of the nicotine obtained by photosynthesis is 160.09 and theory requires 162.13.

4. A probable mechanism for the formation of nicotine in light seems to be the condensation of β -aminopyridine with mucic acid.

5. It appears from our results that the synthesis of nicotine from formaldehyde and nitrite or ammonia requires light and the view that the synthesis of nitrogenous compounds in nature is not photochemical seems to be incorrect.

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